

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Paper

A Review on Assessment of Probiotics Impact on Quality of Life in Elderly Population Using Whoqol-Bref Scale

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 24 Jun. 2025

Keywords:

Probiotics, Aging, Geriatric population, Quality of Life (QoL), Health Related Quality of Life (HRQOL), WHOQOL- BREF Scale

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15730302

ABSTRACT

Promoting healthy aging and improving the quality of life (QOL) in the elderly has emerged as a significant public health priority. Aging is often associated with physiological, psychological, and social changes that can adversely affect overall well-being. The gut microbiota have a large influence on various aspects of health, including digestion, immune function, cognition, and mood. Probiotics are live microorganisms that provide health benefits when consumed in adequate amounts helps to modulate gut microbiota and subsequently support overall health. In older adults, age-related alterations in gut microbiota composition, weakened immune responses, decline in cognitive functions and a higher burden of chronic diseases can contribute to a diminished quality of life. Probiotic supplementation has been proposed as a non-pharmacological strategy to restore microbial balance, strengthen immune function, and potentially enhance mood and cognitive abilities. Collectively, these effects may lead to an improved sense of well-being and greater life satisfaction. The World Health Organization Quality of Life-BREF (WHOQOL-BREF) questionnaire is a widely used tool that evaluates QOL across four key domains: physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environmental factors. Its use in studies assessing probiotic interventions provides valuable insights into the broader connection between gut health and well-being in the geriatric population. This review aims to explore the impact of probiotics on quality of life among older adults, specifically assessed through the WHOQOL-BREF instrument. By analyzing available evidence, this review seeks to clarify the potential role of probiotics in fostering healthy aging and enhancing QOL in the elderly.

INTRODUCTION

Aging is a natural and ongoing part of life, where the body gradually changes over time. It's a process every living being goes through, marked

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

by physical, functional, and sometimes cognitive shifts that reflect the passage of time. In humans, it involves the progressive decline in physiological function, cellular repair, and regeneration. This can lead to increased vulnerability to diseases, decreased physical, mental, social and cognitive abilities, and ultimately leads to death ^[1]. Conditions linked to aging can lead to a decline in physical, social, cognitive and mental functions, impair the ability to carry out daily activities, and result in the loss of roles within the society and personal contentment ^[2]. Elderly population often face multiple chronic conditions, functional limitations, and age-related physiological changes that significantly impact their quality of life. Targeting this group can yield more noticeable improvements in daily living and overall well-being ^[3]. Probiotic use has been proposed as a natural as well as synthetic source in the way to improve gut health, boost immunity, and support better mood and mental clarity. These benefits may work together to improve overall well-being and satisfaction with life. Hence, it is essential to implement probiotics supplementation as treatment strategies that accurately improves health and preserve quality of life ^[4,5,6]. Quality of Life is a dynamic and subjective state of well-being that encompasses an individual's overall satisfaction with life, shaped by the harmony between their physical condition, emotional resilience, meaningful relationships, sense of purpose, and the ability to engage with and adapt to their environment in a way that aligns with personal values and aspirations ^[7]. Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQOL) describes how people

feel about their overall well-being, considering their cultural background, personal values, life goals, and what matters most to them. This is a comprehensive concept influenced by various factors, including physical health, psychological state, level of independence, social relationships, and interactions with key aspects of their environment ^[8]. Life satisfaction assessment is essential in measuring the effectiveness of healthcare, particularly in older adults. One common tool for this purpose is the WHOQOL-BREF, developed by the World Health Organization. This scale evaluates various aspects of life, such as physical health, mental well-being, social relationships, and the environment. For older populations, it's a practical and adaptable tool that helps gauge how interventions or treatments impact their overall well-being and satisfaction with life ^[9,10].

Aging

Aging represents a normal, enduring phase of life common to all people. It brings about gradual changes in the body and mind, making individuals more prone to illnesses and reducing their ability to recover quickly. This process is influenced not only by biology but also by one's genetics, lifestyle, environment, and socioeconomic status. Everyone ages differently, and the effects of aging vary from person to person ^[11,12]. Over the course of aging, various aspects of their health and daily life are affected, as shown in (Figure 1.) These changes occur across several key areas:

Figure 1. Changes during aging

1. Physical and Biological Changes

- **Muscles and Bones:** Muscle mass and bone density naturally decline, which can lead to reduced strength, flexibility, and balance—making movement more difficult.
- **Heart and Blood Vessels:** Blood vessels become stiffer, and the heart may not pump as efficiently, raising the risk of high blood pressure and heart disease.
- **Lungs:** Lung capacity and elasticity decrease, making breathing less effective, especially during physical activity.
- **Immune System:** The immune response weakens with age, leading to a higher risk of infections and a slower healing process.
- **Digestive System:** Digestion can become slower, and nutrient absorption may be less efficient. Changes in gut bacteria and stomach acid levels are also common.

- **Senses:** Vision, hearing, taste, and smell often decline, which can affect communication, appetite, and enjoyment of daily life.
- **Skin and Hair:** As we age, the skin tends to lose its firmness and becomes more delicate, often resulting in wrinkles and a less youthful appearance. Hair may turn gray or fall out over time ^[13,14].

2. Cognitive and Neurological Changes:

- **Memory:** Many older adults notice changes in memory, especially short-term memory, and slower information processing.
- **Thinking Skills:** Tasks that involve planning, decision-making, or handling multiple things at once may become more difficult.
- **Brain Health:** As people get older, their chances of developing memory-related conditions like Alzheimer's and other forms of dementia become higher.

- **Sleep:** Sleep patterns often shift, leading to lighter, more fragmented sleep and earlier waking hours ^[15,16].

3. Psychological and Emotional Changes:

- **Mental Well-Being:** Older adults may be more prone to depression, anxiety, or loneliness, especially after losing loved ones or facing health issues.
- **Emotional Resilience:** While some find greater emotional balance with age, adapting to change can become more challenging.
- **Sense of Identity:** Major life transitions like retirement or changes in physical ability—can affect self-esteem and how individuals see themselves ^[17,18].

4. Social and Environmental Changes:

- **Relationships and Roles:** Retirement, caregiving duties, or the loss of a spouse or peers can shift social roles and support networks.
- **Living Situation:** Many older adults live alone or in assisted facilities, which can affect their sense of independence and comfort.
- **Finances:** A fixed income or financial reliance on others can limit access to healthcare and social opportunities.

- **Isolation:** Smaller social circles or reduced mobility can lead to loneliness and a decline in mental health ^[19,20].

5. Functional Decline and Quality of Life:

- **Basic Daily Tasks (ADLs):** Activities like bathing, dressing, or feeding oneself can become more difficult.
- **Complex Daily Tasks (IADLs):** Managing medications, money, or transportation may require help.
- **Overall Well-being:** All these changes together can influence a person's independence, autonomy, and satisfaction with life ^[21,22].

Advancing age affects far more than just the body it shapes every part of a person's life. Being aware of these shifts is vital for ensuring a positive and enriched aging experience. With the right care, understanding, and resources, older adults can continue to live with dignity, purpose, and a good quality of life ^[23].

Geriatric Population

The geriatric population comprises individuals aged 65 years and above, marked by age-related physiological, functional, and cognitive changes that impact their healthcare needs ^[24,25]. This group is commonly classified into two: age based classification and functional classification as shown in (*Figure 2.*)

Figure 2. Geriatric population classification based on age and functionality

1. Age-Based Classification

During aging, their experiences, health, and abilities can vary greatly. Here's a look at the different age groups within the older population and what typically characterizes them:

- **Young-Old (65–74 years):** Elderly individuals in this group are still healthy and active. They often live independently, remain socially engaged, and may even continue working or volunteering.
- **Middle-Old (75–84 years):** This stage often brings the onset of chronic health issues like high blood pressure or diabetes. Some may begin to notice changes in physical strength or memory, though many still manage their daily lives with minimal assistance.
- **Oldest-Old (85+ years):** People in this group tend to be more vulnerable. They are more likely to experience physical weakness, memory challenges, and require support with daily activities. Conditions like dementia and osteoporosis become more common.

- **Centenarians (100+ years):** Turning 100 is an extraordinary achievement. While some centenarians remain mentally sharp and fairly independent, others may face significant cognitive or physical decline. Their longevity is often associated with a mix of good genes, a healthy lifestyle, and low stress.
- **Supercentenarians (110+ years):** This group of elderly people are rare who lives more than 110 years. Their longevity stands out as a remarkable example of human lifespan potential. Interestingly, many stay relatively healthy and free from serious illness until quite late in life, defying the usual expectations of aging^[26,27].

2. Functional Classification

As people grow older, their ability to live independently and handle everyday tasks can differ greatly from one person to another. This classification helps us understand the different stages of functional ability among older adults:

- **Robust Elderly:** These individuals remain active and independent, managing their daily routines with little to no difficulty. They may

have chronic health conditions, but these are usually well controlled and don't interfere significantly with daily life or self-care.

- **Pre-Frail Elderly:** This group is beginning to show early signs of physical or functional decline, such as slower movement or increased tiredness. While they can still manage most tasks, they might occasionally need help with more complex responsibilities like managing medications or finances. Even small health issues could push them toward greater frailty.
- **Frail Elderly:** These individuals experience noticeable physical weakness and are more vulnerable to health problems. They often struggle with weight loss, fatigue, and slower movement. Their risk of falling, hospitalization, or loss of independence is higher. Many require help with both basic tasks (like bathing or dressing) and more involved ones (like cooking or shopping).
- **Dependent Elderly:** This group needs regular support for everyday tasks due to serious physical or mental health challenges. They may be unable to care for themselves without help and often rely on caregivers or long-term care facilities. Conditions like advanced dementia, stroke, or severe disability are common, and some may be bedridden or fully dependent on others. [28,29].

Impact of Aging On Drug Kinetics

The natural changes in our bodies can have a big impact on how medications work and how our body responds to them. These changes affect every stage from how drugs enter the body to how they're removed [30,31].

Absorption

- Gastric acid production declines, leading to altered drug solubility.
- Delayed gastric emptying and reduced splanchnic blood flow may slightly slow absorption.
- Intestinal surface area may decrease, but overall drug absorption is often not significantly impaired.
- Conditions like achlorhydria and bacterial overgrowth can affect the bioavailability of some drugs (e.g., calcium carbonate, digoxin).

Distribution

- Increased body fat alters the volume of distribution (Vd) for lipophilic drugs (e.g., diazepam), prolonging their half-life.
- Decreased lean body mass and total body water reduce Vd for hydrophilic drugs (e.g., aminoglycosides), possibly increasing plasma concentration.
- Lower serum albumin levels can affect protein binding, increasing free (active) drug levels for highly protein-bound drugs (e.g., phenytoin, warfarin).

Metabolism

- Liver size and hepatic blood flow decrease, especially impacting first-pass metabolism.
- Phase I reactions (oxidation, reduction, hydrolysis), often catalyzed by cytochrome P450 enzymes, may be slowed.
- Phase II reactions (conjugation: glucuronidation, sulfation) are usually preserved.
- Some drugs may have prolonged half-lives and increased plasma levels (e.g., theophylline, propranolol).

Excretion:

- Renal function typically declines with age, even without overt disease.

- Glomerular filtration rate (GFR), renal blood flow, and tubular function are reduced.
- Drugs primarily excreted by the kidneys (e.g., aminoglycosides, digoxin, lithium) may accumulate, increasing the risk of toxicity.
- Creatinine clearance (CrCl) should be estimated (e.g., via Cockcroft-Gault formula) for proper dose adjustments, as serum creatinine alone may not reflect renal function in older adults due to reduced muscle mass [30,31].

Impact Of Aging On Drug Response

Pharmacodynamics is the study of how the body reacts to medications and how those drugs produce their effects. During aging, these responses can shift noticeably [32,33].

- **Increased Sensitivity:** Older individuals may be more affected by certain drugs, such as blood thinners, pain relievers, or sleep aids. This heightened sensitivity can make them more vulnerable to side effects like excessive drowsiness, difficulty breathing, or an increased risk of bleeding.
- **Reduced Effectiveness:** Aging reduces the body's ability to compensate for drug induced changes. Some drugs, like beta-blockers, may not work as well in the elderly. This is partly due to changes in how the body's cells respond to these medications.
- **Weakened Balance Systems:** aged people can make it harder for the body to maintain internal balance, making older individuals more prone to issues like sudden drops in blood pressure with antihypertensives or low blood sugar from diabetes medications [32,33].

Role of Probiotics In Improving Quality Of Life In Geriatric Population

Probiotics are viable microorganisms that, when taken adequately enhance the health of the host. They are inherently non-pathogenic and contribute positively to host well-being. Aging-related dysbiosis refers to an imbalance or disturbance in the structure and function of the gut microbiota. This condition is characterized by a reduction in microbial diversity, an excessive proliferation of potentially harmful bacteria, accompanied by a reduction in beneficial microbes. Thus, the probiotics play a vital role in enhancing digestive health, immune function and cognitive function by maintaining a balanced gut microbiota [34]. Gut microbial enhancers support digestive health by reinforcing the gut epithelial barrier, strengthening the intestinal lining, stimulating the secretion of mucins and defensins, and preventing harmful substances from leaking into the bloodstream (a condition known as leaky gut). They also enhance adhesion to the intestinal mucosa by binding to the intestinal surface, promoting colonization and stability, and inhibit pathogen attachment to epithelial cells by occupying available binding sites [35]. Competitive exclusion of pathogenic microorganisms by outcompete with the harmful microbes for nutrients and space, reducing gastrointestinal symptoms like constipation and diarrhea in conditions like IBD, *Clostridium difficile* or *helicobacter pylori* associated infections, gastroenteritis, gastritis and enteric fever. It generates the lactase enzyme, facilitating the digestion of dairy products in individuals with lactose intolerance, while also enhancing nutrient absorption [36]. Production of anti-microorganism substances by secreting antimicrobial compounds that inhibit pathogen growth. Immune system modulation occurs through interactions with dendritic cells (DCs) and macrophages in the lamina propria, influencing the production of cytokines (such as IL-10 and TGF- β), which in

turn regulate the differentiation of immune cells (Treg, Th1, Th2, Th17), thereby shaping immune responses. Normal flora balancers strengthen immune function by stimulating the production of immune cells like macrophages, dendritic cells, and natural killer (NK) cells and boosting the body's ability to fight infections. They also reinforce the intestinal barrier, preventing the entry of harmful pathogens and toxins into the bloodstream. Probiotic strains modulate the production of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines, helping control chronic inflammation and promoting immune balance^[37]. Live beneficial microorganisms can increase the levels of immunoglobulin A (IgA) in the mucosa, which is important for neutralizing pathogens at entry points like the gut and respiratory tract. This flora-friendly microbes can assist the immune system in distinguishing between harmful and harmless agents, thereby potentially minimizing allergic reactions and autoimmune responses.

Probiotic supplementation also enhance the efficacy of vaccines by improving the body's immune response to the antigens^[38]. Functional microbes improve cognitive function by influencing the gut-brain axis, the bidirectional communication network between the gut and the brain by enhancing the gut barrier and blood-brain barrier integrity by preventing harmful substances from reaching the brain and affecting neurological function. It can produce or influence neurotransmitters like serotonin, dopamine, and GABA, which regulate mood, memory, and cognition and immune responses through inflammatory cytokines and immune cells^[39]. Within the gut lumen, short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) and neurotransmitters are also produced by the intestinal epithelium, contributing to this complex interaction. It can also can modulate the HPA (hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal) axis, reducing stress hormone (cortisol) levels and improving resilience to stress^[40].

Figure 3. Demonstration of interconnected benefits of probiotics

Together, these effects demonstrate the interconnected benefits of probiotics (*Figure 3.*) across multiple systems. This results in improved quality of life and better overall health particularly beneficial in elderly individuals^[41,42].

Assessment of Quality Of Life In Geriatric Population Using Whoqol- Bref Scale

Quality Of Life And Health Related Quality Of Life

Quality of Life (QoL) pertains to holistic wellbeing, spanning bodily health, emotional balance and social engagement. Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQoL) specifically focuses on how health status that is both physical and mental aspect impacts on a person's ability to live a fulfilling life. It is a key indicator used to assess the effectiveness of healthcare interventions and the overall burden of disease^[43,44].

Need Of Improvement Of Quality Of Life In Geriatric Population When Compared To Other Populations

The geriatric population generally includes individuals who are 65 years of age or older. The geriatric population is widely recognized as one of the most vulnerable groups when it comes to quality of life. Aging is often accompanied by multiple chronic health conditions, reduced physiological reserve, cognitive decline, and functional impairments, all of which can negatively impact daily living and independence. In addition, older adults are more susceptible to psychosocial challenges such as social isolation, bereavement, depression, and reduced economic stability following retirement^[45]. They faces unique challenges that significantly impact their quality of life more than other age groups. The geriatric population experiences a range of age-related physiological, psychological, and social changes that significantly affect their quality of life, more so than other age groups^[46]. With advancing age, the prevalence of chronic illnesses such as hypertension, diabetes, arthritis, and cognitive impairments like dementia increases. These health challenges often lead to reduced mobility, dependency, and frequent hospital visits. Unlike younger populations who typically enjoy better physical health and social integration, elderly individuals often face functional decline

and a loss of independence. This makes it imperative to focus on improving their overall well-being through appropriate medical care, rehabilitation, and social support systems^[47]. Enhancing the quality of life in older adults is essential because:

- **Increased Life Expectancy:** With global aging, a longer lifespan does not necessarily equate to a healthier life unless accompanied by improved well-being.
- **Higher Disease Burden:** Older adults are more susceptible to chronic diseases like arthritis, diabetes, cardiovascular conditions, and neurodegenerative disorders.
- **Psychosocial Challenges:** Loneliness, depression, and cognitive impairments like dementia are more prevalent, affecting mental health and life satisfaction.
- **Economic and Care Burden:** Without improved quality of life, the economic burden on families and healthcare systems increases due to frequent hospitalizations and long-term care.
- **Right to Dignity:** Growing older with dignity and independence is a fundamental human right, highlighting the importance of personalized healthcare, social inclusion, and supportive environments^[48].

The people in later adult hood often face a compression of support, a shrinking social circle due to the loss of peers and changing family dynamics making them more susceptible to neglect, depression, and dependency. In contrast, other age groups typically benefit from stronger social networks and better health reserves. Improving the quality of life in geriatric

individuals thus requires a multidimensional strategy that is integrating palliative care, geriatric mental health, accessibility improvements, age-friendly environments, and policies that prioritize aging in place with dignity and purpose [49]. In addition to physical health concerns, the elderly frequently encounters mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, and loneliness, often exacerbated by the loss of a spouse or reduced family interaction. These psychosocial factors further deteriorate their quality of life and may go unnoticed or untreated [50]. Enhancing quality of life in the elderly, therefore, requires a holistic approach that addresses not only medical needs but also emotional and social well-being. Compared to other populations, the geriatric group has unique needs that demand specialized care models, community-based support, and policy-level interventions to promote healthy and dignified aging [51]. These combined physical, mental, and social factors increase the risk of diminished well-being and life satisfaction in later years. Moreover, the geriatric population often faces barriers to accessing healthcare, nutritional support, and social services, making them more reliant on public health interventions and caregiving systems. Given their increased needs and limited adaptability, improving the quality of life in elderly individuals is a public health priority

that requires a multidimensional, patient-centered approach [52].

WHO QOL- BREF SCALE

The WHO developed WHOQOL-BREF is a globally recognized tool developed by the World Health Organization to explore how individuals feel about different aspects of their lives. It's designed to be used across various cultures and health conditions, offering a broad and inclusive understanding of a person's overall well-being from physical and emotional health to social relationships and daily environment [53]. It is a shortened version of the original WHOQOL-100 and consists of 26 items, covering four key domains as shown in the (table 1.) that is physical health, physiological health, social relationships and environmental quality of life. Additionally, the WHO-BREF includes two global questions that is one assessing the individual's general perception of quality of life and the other evaluating overall well-being and health [54]. The quality of assessment tool is culturally sensitive and has been validated in multiple languages, making it suitable for global use in both clinical and research settings. The WHOQOL-BREF is designed to capture the individual's subjective perspective on their life, rather than relying solely on objective health indicators [55].

Table 1. Domains of WHOQOL BREF Scale

Domain	Facet	Question number in the WHOQOL- BREF
Global items	Overall quality of life	1
Physical health	General health	2
	Pain and discomfort	3
	Dependence on medical substances and medical aids	4
	Energy and fatigue	10
	Mobility	15
	Sleep and rest	16
	Activities of daily living	17
	Work capacity	18

Physiological health	Positive feelings	5
	Spirituality, religion and personal beliefs	6
	Thinking, learning, memory and concentration	7
	Bodily image and appearance	11
	Self-esteem	19
	Negative feelings	26
Social relationships	Personal relationships	20
	Sexual activity	21
	Social support	22
Environmental Quality of life	Freedom, physical safety and security	8
	Physical environment (pollution/noise/traffic/climate)	9
	Financial resources	12
	Opportunities for acquiring new information and skills	13
	Participation in and opportunities for recreation	14
	Home environment	23
	Health and social care; accessibility and quality	24
Transport	25	

It provides a holistic view of well-being by encompassing not only physical health but also emotional status, social support, and environmental factors such as financial security and access to healthcare. The questionnaire is meant to be filled out by individuals themselves and typically takes less than 10 minutes to complete. Its psychometric strength, ease of use, and global adaptability make it a valuable tool in assessing quality of life among diverse populations, including patients with chronic illness, the elderly, and the general public [56].

- The **physical domain** (7 items) assesses aspects such as physical functioning (energy levels, fatigue, mobility, sleep and rest, activities of daily living, work capacity) and pain and discomfort.
- The **physiological health domain** (6 items) assesses aspects such as mental well-being (including positive and negative emotions), spirituality, religious beliefs, personal values, cognitive functions (such as thinking, learning,

memory, and concentration), body image, physical appearance, and self-esteem.

- The **social relationships domain** (3 items) measures personal relationships, sexual activity, social support, and an individual's ability to engage in social activities.
- The **environmental health domain** (8 items) focuses on the surrounding environment, considering factors like freedom, physical safety, security, physical environment (pollution/ noise/ traffic/ climate), financial resources, opportunities for acquiring new information and skills, participation in and opportunities for recreation, home environment, health and social care; accessibility and quality and transport.
- Furthermore, two general questions evaluate **overall quality of life** and **general health satisfaction** [57,58].

All these domains work together to shape a person's overall sense of well-being and daily functioning, with positive changes in any area contributing to a more fulfilling and comfortable

life^[58]. This scale provides a clear way to assess quality of life by considering physical health, mental state, social relationships, and the living environment. Focusing on these key areas allows for a fuller understanding of an individual's well-being, highlighting the importance of improving all aspects of life^[59]. The scoring and interpretation is based on the measure of response on a 5-point scale ranging from 1-5, with higher scores indicating better quality of life. The scores for each domain's score is determined by computing the average of the responses to the items it contains. It generates a composite score

reflecting each of the four dimensions. Except pain and discomfort (3), dependence on medical substances and medical aids (4) and negative feelings (26) sub domains are reverse or back scored and other sub domains are original scoring domains^[60]. Each item is scored on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = very poor/dissatisfied to 5 = very good/satisfied). To get the score for each area, the individual responses within that section are added together. The raw scores are standardized on a scale from 0-100, where higher scores indicating a more favourable quality of life^[61]. The (Table 2.) shows the formula for calculating each domain:

Table 2. Each domains score calculating formula

Domains	Scoring
Physical Domain	{Sum of individual scores of sub domain – 7} divided by 28 and multiplied with 100
Physiological Domain	{Sum of individual scores of sub domain – 6} divided by 24 and multiplied with 100
Social Relationships	{Sum of individual scores of sub domain – 3} divided by 12 and multiplied with 100
Environmental Quality of life	{Sum of individual scores of sub domain – 8} divided by 32 and multiplied with 100

Higher domain specific scores are associated with a strong sense of life quality. Lower scores suggest limitations, dissatisfaction, or poor functioning in the respective domain. Domain scores are interpreted individually; there is no single total score. Results can be compared across populations, used to monitor changes over time, or evaluate the effectiveness of interventions^[62]. For the geriatric population, achieving balance across these domains is crucial for enhancing quality of life. Tackling physical health issues, promoting psychological well-being, nurturing social connections, and improving environmental factors all play a role in fostering better aging experiences, enabling older adults to sustain independence and a high quality of life^[63]. The WHOQOL-BREF scale plays a crucial role in evaluating the impact

of probiotics on the quality of life in the geriatric population by assessing improvements across physical, psychological, social, and environmental domains. Probiotics can enhance gut health, which may lead to better digestion, mood, and overall well-being, thus improving scores in the physical and psychological health domains. By monitoring these changes with the WHOQOL-BREF, can analyze the impact of probiotic intervention in the quality of life of geriatric population and that foster greater independence and life satisfaction in older adults^[64,65].

DISCUSSION

With the global increase in aging populations, maintaining quality of life (QoL) in the elderly has

become a priority. Aging is associated with physiological changes, immune decline, and gut microbiota dysbiosis, all of which can impact health outcomes and overall well-being. Probiotics have shown potential in restoring gut microbial balance, enhancing immune responses, and reducing gastrointestinal symptoms, which are common among the elderly. Multiple studies have evaluated the role of probiotics in mitigating age-related health issues, including irritable bowel syndrome, depression, and inflammation. These effects contribute positively to both physical and psychological domains of QoL. Moreover, the gut-brain axis highlights a strong link between microbial health and mental well-being, suggesting that probiotics may influence mood and cognition in older adults. To measure these multidimensional impacts, the WHOQOL-BREF scale developed by the World Health Organization is widely used for assessing QoL across physical, psychological, social, and environmental domains. Its validated versions in different cultural contexts make it a reliable tool for elderly populations globally. Several pilot and clinical studies have employed WHOQOL-BREF to quantify the benefits of probiotic supplementation, reporting improvements in digestive comfort, mood, energy levels, and social engagement among older adults. These findings support the integration of probiotics into geriatric care as a non-invasive, adjunctive approach to improve QoL. These evidences suggest that probiotics may serve as a supportive intervention to enhance the quality of life in elderly populations. The WHOQOL-BREF scale provides a validated framework to evaluate these benefits holistically.

CONCLUSION

Assessing the impact of probiotics on the quality of life in the elderly using the WHOQOL-BREF

scale provides valuable insights into how gut health influences overall well-being. Probiotic supplementation may contribute to improvements in physical health, psychological stability, and social functioning. The WHOQOL-BREF scale, with its multidimensional approach, serves as an effective tool for measuring these changes, highlighting the potential role of probiotics in enhancing health-related quality of life among the aging population.

REFERENCES

1. Jun Guo, Xiuqing Huang; et al; Aging and aging-related diseases: from molecular mechanisms to interventions and treatments; *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy*; 2022; 7(391); <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-022-01251-0>.
2. Li Z, Zhang Z, Ren Y, Wang Y, Fang J, Yue H, Ma S, Guan F. Aging and age-related diseases: from mechanisms to therapeutic strategies. *Biogerontology*. 2021;22(2):165-187; doi:10.1007/s10522-021-099105; <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7838467/>.
3. Ismail Z, Ahmad WIW; et al; The Impact of Population Ageing: A Review; *Iran J Public Health*; 2021;50(12):24512460; doi:10.18502/ijph.v50i12.7927; <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9577145/>.
4. Chen Gao; et al; The Importance of Probiotics from Digestion to Immunity and Mental Health; *Journal of Probiotics & Health*; 2024; 12(4); 360; <https://www.longdom.org/open-access/the-importance-of-probiotics-from-digestion-to-immunity-and-mental-health-110751.html>.
5. Merve İnce P, Gizem Kose; et al; Probiotics and Prebiotics Affecting Mental and Gut Health;

- mdpi; *Healthcare* 2024, 12(5); 510; <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare12050510>.
6. Yan F, Polk DB; et al; Probiotics and immune health; *Curr Opin Gastroenterol*; 2011;27(6):496-501;doi:10.1097/MOG.0b013e32834baa4d; <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4006993/>.
7. Tommaso Cai, Paolo Verze; et al; The Quality of Life Definition: Where Are We Going? *mdpi; Uro* 2021, 1(1), 14-22; <https://doi.org/10.3390/uro1010003>.
8. Sitlinger A, Zafar SY; et al; Health-Related Quality of Life: The Impact on Morbidity and Mortality; *Surg Oncol Clin N Am*;2018 ;27(4):675-684; doi: 10.1016/j.soc.2018.05.008; <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6428416/>.
9. Gholami A, Jahromi LM; et al; Application of WHOQOL-BREF in Measuring Quality of Life in Health Care Staff; *Int J. Prev. Med*;2013;4(7):80917; <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3775221/>.
10. Fiona Y Wong, Lin Yang ; et al; Assessing quality of life using WHOQOL-BREF: A cross-sectional study on the association between quality of life and neighborhood environmental satisfaction, and the mediating effect of health-related behaviors; *BMC Public Health*;2018; 18: 1113 ;<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-5942-3>.
11. Carlos L, Linda Partridge; et al; Hallmark of aging: An expanding universe; *Cell*;2023;186(2);243-78; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2022.11.001>.
12. Claudio F, Paolo G; et al; The Continuum of Aging and Age-Related Diseases: Common Mechanisms but Different Rates; *Geriatric Medicine*;2018;5(61);<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/medicine/articles/10.3389/fmed.2018.00061/full>.
13. Boss GR, Seegmiller JE; et al; Age-related physiological changes and their clinical significance; *West. J. Med*;1981;135(6):434-40; <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1273316/>.
14. Joanna Preston, Bryonnie Biddell; et al; The physiology of ageing and how these changes affect older people; *Medicine*;2021;49(1);1-5;ISSN1357-3039;<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mpm.2020.10.011>.
15. Meghraj Singh Baghel, Padmanabh Singh; Cognitive Changes with Aging; *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci., India, Sect. B Biol. Sci*;springer; 2017;221(5); <https://doi:10.1007/s40011-017-0906-4>.
16. Lee J, Kim HJ; et al; Normal Aging Induces Changes in the Brain and Neurodegeneration Progress: Review of the Structural, Biochemical, Metabolic, Cellular, and Molecular Changes; *Front. Aging. Neurosci*;2022; 14:931536;2022; <https://doi:10.3389/fnagi.2022.931536>.
17. Mitina M, Young S, Zhavoronkov A; et al; Psychological aging, depression, and well-being; *Aging (Albany NY)*; 2020;12(18):18765-18777;<https://doi:10.18632/aging.103880>.
18. Scheibe S, Carstensen LL; et al; Emotional aging: recent findings and future trends; *J. Gerontol. B. Psychol. Sci. Soc. Sci*;2010;65B(2);135144;<https://doi:10.1093/geronb/gbp132>.
19. Hua, K., Pan, Y., Fang, J; et al; Integrating social, climate and environmental changes to confront accelerating global aging;

- BMCPublicHealth;2024;24;2838;
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-20346-7>.
20. Teresa E Seeman, Eileen Crimmins; etal; Social environment effects on health and aging: integrating epidemiologic and demographic approaches and perspectives; *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*;2001; 954 (1);88-117; <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.2001.tb02749.x>.
21. Palgi, Y., Shrira, A; etal; Quality of life attenuates age-related decline in functional status of older adults; *Qual Life Res*; 2015;24;1835–1843; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-015-0918-6>.
22. M.M. Wallen Hansen, A.H.Ranhoff; etal; Health-related quality of life, functional decline, and long-term mortality in older patients following hospitalisation due to COVID-19;*BMC Geriatrics* ;2021; 21(199);<https://bmcgeriatr.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12877-021-02140-x>.
23. Dong Choon Park, Seung Geun Yeo; etal;Aging; *Korean J Audiol*; 2013;17:39-44; <http://dx.doi.org/10.7874/kja.2013.17.2.39>.
24. Malik C, Khanna S; etal; Geriatric population in India: Demography, vulnerabilities, and healthcare challenges; *J Family Med Prim Care*; 2021;10(1):72-76; doi: 10.4103/jfmpe.jfmpe_1794_20.
25. A.D. John, Frederick E. Sieber; etal; Age associated issues: geriatrics; *Anesthesiology Clinics of North America*; 2004; 22 (1); 45-58; [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-8537\(03\)00119-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-8537(03)00119-6).
26. Lee SB, Oh JH, Wee JH; etal; Differences in youngest-old, middle-old, and oldest-old patients who visit the emergency department; *Clin Exp Emerg Med*; 2018;5(4):249-255; <https://doi.org/10.15441/ceem.17.261>.
27. Giri S, Al-Obaidi M, Weaver A; etal; Association Between Chronologic Age and Geriatric Assessment-Identified Impairments: Findings From the CARE Registry;*J Natl Compr Canc Netw*; 2021 ;19(8):922-927; <https://doi.org/10.6004/jnccn.2020.7679>.
28. Han Y, Zhang L; etal; Novel subgroups of functional ability in older adults and their associations with adverse outcomes; *BMC Geriatr*; 2022;22(1):390; <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12877-022-03081-9>.
29. Hoogendijk EO, Romero L; etal; A New Functional Classification Based on Frailty and Disability Stratifies the Risk for Mortality Among Older Adults: The FRADEA Study; *J.Am.Med. Dir.Assoc*;2019;20(9):1105-1110; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jamda.2019.01.129>.
30. Crooks, J, O'Malley, K; etal; Pharmacokinetics in the Elderly;*Clin Pharmacokinet*;1976; 1; 280–296 ; <https://doi.org/10.2165/00003088-197601040-00003>.
31. Jordan L. Cohen; etal; Pharmacokinetic changes in aging;*American Journal of Medicine*; 1986;80(5); 31-38; [https://www.amjmed.com/article/0002-9343\(86\)90535-8](https://www.amjmed.com/article/0002-9343(86)90535-8).
32. Bowie MW, Slattum PW; etal; Pharmacodynamics in older adults: a review; *Am J Geriatr Pharmacother*: 2007 ;(3):263-303; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjopharm.2007.10.001>.
33. Ngcobo, N.N; etal; Influence of Ageing on the Pharmacodynamics and Pharmacokinetics of Chronically Administered Medicines in Geriatric Patients: A Review; *Clin Pharmacokinet*;2025; 64;335–367; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40262-024-01466-0>.
34. Bhutada Sarita, Dahika Samadhan; etal; A comprehensive review of probiotics and

- human health-currentprospective and applications; *Front.Microbiol*;2025;15; <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2024.1487641>.
35. Eamonn M.M. Qulgley ; Probiotics and Probiotics in Digestive Health; microbiome directedtherapies:pastpresentandfuture;2019;17(2);333344;[https://www.cghjournal.org/article/S1542-3565\(18\)31019-X](https://www.cghjournal.org/article/S1542-3565(18)31019-X).
36. Seon-Kyun Kim, Robin B. Guevarra; etal; Role of Probiotics in Human Gut Microbiome-AssociatedDiseases; *J. Microbiol.Biotechnol*;2019;29(9):1335-40; <https://doi.org/10.4014/jmb.1906.06064>.
37. Mazziotta C, Tognon M; etal;Probiotics Mechanism of Action on Immune Cells and BeneficialEffectsonHumanHealth;*Cells*;2023;12(1):184;<https://doi:10.3390/cells12010184>.
38. Yue Liu, Jiaqi Wang ; Modulation of Gut Microbiota and Immune System by Probiotics, Prebiotics,andPostbiotics;*Front.Nutr*;2022;8;634897;<https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2021.634897>.
39. Kumar A, Sivamaruthi BS, Dey S; et al; Probiotics as modulators of gut-brain axis for cognitive development, *Front.Pharmacol*;2024;15:1348297;<https://doi:10.3389/fphar.2024.1348297>.
40. Kim CS, Cha L, Sim M; etal; Probiotic Supplementation Improves Cognitive Function and Mood with Changes in Gut Microbiota in Community-Dwelling Older Adults: A Randomized, Double-Blind, Placebo-Controlled, Multicenter Trial; *J Gerontol A Biol Sci Med Sci*;2021;76(1):32-40;<https://doi:10.1093/gerona/glaa090>.
41. Hemarajata P, Versalovic J; etal; Effects of probiotics on gut microbiota: mechanisms of intestinal immunomodulation and neuromodulation; *Therap Adv Gastroenterol*; 2013;6(1):39-51; <https://doi:10.1177/1756283X12459294>.
42. Nicoleta Maricica Maftei, Monica Boev;etal; The Potential Impact of Probiotics on Human Health: An Update on Their Health-Promoting Properties; *mdpi;Microorganisms*; 2024;12(2); 234;<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms12020234>.
43. Patrick Jones , Peter D. Drummond; etal; A Summary of Current Findings on Quality of Life Domains and a Proposal for Their Inclusion in Clinical Interventions; *Front. Psychol*; 2021;12; <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.747435>.
44. Robert M Kaplan, Ron D Hays ; etal; Health-Related Quality of Life Measurement in Public Health; *annual review of public health*; 2022;43;355-373; <https://www.annualreviews.org/content/journals/10.1146/annurev-publhealth-052120-012811>.
45. Premnath Dhasaram, Lalithambigai Chellamuthu;etal; Assessment of Quality of Life and Determinants Among the Elderly Population in Rural Areas of Puducherry: A Mixed Method Study;*Journal of Medical Sciences*;2024; 2(11); 1146–1156; <https://doi:10.61770/NBEJMS.2024.v02.i11.09>.
46. Rajput M, Pinki; etal; Determinants of quality of life of geriatric population in rural block of Haryana;*J Family Med Prim Care*; 2022;11(9);5103-5109;https://doi:10.4103/jfmprc.jfmprc_1943_21.
47. Vignesh, Nawin Jai; etal; A Comparative Study on Quality of Life of Elderly among those Living with Families and in Old Age Homes in a District in South India;*Journal of*

- the Indian Academy of Geriatrics;2022;18(4);[https://doi: 196-200;10.4103/jiag.jiag_40_22](https://doi.org/10.4103/jiag.jiag_40_22).
48. Trivedi B; etal; Quality of life among geriatric population residing in Bhavnagar city, Gujarat, WesternIndia; *J.Family.Med.Prim.Care*;2023;12(5):925-31;[https://doi:10.4103/jfmprc.jfmprc_1592_22](https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmprc.jfmprc_1592_22).
49. Inga Izdonaite Medziuniene; Laura Preiksaitiene; etal; Disposition of improving quality of life in older adults: the case of Lithuania; *Aging Clin Exp Res*; 2024; 36;26; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40520-023-02687-2>.
50. Vinay Godara, Chetan Kumar Sharma; etal; Ageing and Quality of Life among Elderly Population in Field Practice Area of Department of Community Medicine; *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*; 2023; 15(5); 901-10; [https://doi: e-ISSN: 0975-1556, p-ISSN: 2820-2643](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40520-023-02687-2).
51. Mohammed Ullah, Rina Parvin; etal; Challenges and Advancements in the Health-Related Quality of Life of Older People; *advances in public health*; 2024;1; 8839631; <https://doi.org/10.1155/2024/8839631>.
52. Krishnappa, Lalitha;etal; Quality of life (QOL) among older persons in an urban and rural area of Bangalore, South India;*Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*; 2021;10(1);272-277;[https://doi: 10.4103/jfmprc.jfmprc_1241_20](https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmprc.jfmprc_1241_20).
53. Vahedi S; etal;World Health Organization Quality-of-Life Scale (WHOQOL-BREF): Analyses of Their Item Response Theory Properties Based on the Graded Responses Model;*Iran J Psychiatry*; 2010;5(4):140-153;<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3395923/>.
54. Amer A, Afif Ben S; etal; Validity and reliability of the WHOQOL-BREF in the measurement of the quality of life of Sickle disease patients in Bahrain; *Front. Psychol*; 2023; 14; <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1219576>.
55. Krageloh CU, Henning MA; etal; Validation of the WHOQOL-BREF quality of life questionnaire for use with medical students;*Educ Health (Abingdon)*;2011;24(2):545;https://journals.lww.com/edhe/fulltext/2011/24020/validation_of_the_whoqol_bref_quality_of_life.11.aspx.
56. Kalfoss MH, Reidunsdatter RJ; etal; Validation of the WHOQOL-Bref: psychometric properties and normative data for the Norwegian general population; *Health Qual Life Outcomes*; 2021;19(1):13; [https://doi:10.1186/s12955-020-01656-x](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12955-020-01656-x).
57. Skevington SM, Lotfy M; etal; WHOQOL Group. The World Health Organization's WHOQOL-BREF quality of life assessment: psychometric properties and results of the international field trial;*Qual Life Res*; 2004;13(2):299–310;<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15085902/>.
58. Berlim MT, Pavanello DP; etal;Reliability and validity of the WHOQOL BREF in a sample of Brazilian outpatients with major depression; *Qual Life Res*; 2005;14(2):561-4;[https://doi: 10.1007/s11136-004-4694-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-004-4694-y). PMID: 15892446.
59. Nayak J, Kamath A; etal; A study on the quality of life among the elderly in a rural population of Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka, India;*J Clin Diagn Res*;2014 ;8(1):JC01–JC03;<https://www.academia.edu/74187387>.

60. Saffari M, Chang KC; et al. Sleep Quality and Self-Stigma Mediate the Association Between Problematic Use of Social Media and Quality of Life Among People With Schizophrenia in Taiwan: A Longitudinal Study; *Psychiatry Investig*; 2023;20(11):1034-1044; <https://doi.org/10.30773/pi.2023.0169>.
61. Salmon P, Manzi F; et al; Measuring the meaning of life for patients with incurable cancer: the life evaluation questionnaire (LEQ);*Eur J Cancer*; 1996;32A(5):755-60; [https://doi.org/10.1016/0959-8049\(95\)00643-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0959-8049(95)00643-5).
62. Hawthorne, G., Herrman, H; et al; Interpreting the WHOQOL-Brèf: Preliminary Population Norms and Effect Sizes;*Soc Indic Res*;2006; 77; 37–59; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-005-5552-1>.
63. WHO; The World Health Organization Quality of Life Assessment (WHOQOL): development and general psychometric properties;*Soc Sci Med.* 1998 ;46(12):1569-85;[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0277-9536\(98\)00009-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0277-9536(98)00009-4).
64. West EC, Williams LJ;etal; Quality of life in south-eastern Australia: normative values for the WHOQOL-BREF in a population-based sample of adults;*BMJ*; 2023;13(12):e073556; <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2023-073556>.
65. Hawthorne, G; et al; Measuring Social Isolation in Older Adults: Development and Initial Validation of the Friendship Scale. *Soc Indic Res* ;2006;77; 521–48; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-005-7746-y>.

HOW TO CITE: Ardra S. A., Amina S. N., Sam Jeeva Kumar*, Chintha Chandran, Shaiju S. Dharan, A Review on Assessment of Probiotics Impact on Quality of Life in Elderly Population Using Whoqol-Bref Scale, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 6, 3939-3956. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15730302>

